

Optimization of N fertilizer dose to increase potato yield and profits in farmer's field

Sandip Timilsina^{1*}, Asmita Khanal¹ and CK Timilsina²

¹Horticultural Research Station, Pokhara, Kaski

²Directorate of Agricultural Research, Gandaki Province, Lumle, Kaski

*Email: sandiptimilsina@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Potatoes are the most important staple food crop and play a vital role in ensuring national food security in Nepal. The appropriate dose of fertilizers for potato varies with soil, agroecology, and crop management practices. Optimizing N fertilization is critical to reduce the loss to the environment and increase crop yields, nitrogen use efficiency (NUE), and net profit to farmers. An experiment was carried out to determine the optimal dose of N to increase potato yield, NUE, and net profits in the farmer's field at Machhapuchhre 06 Kaski, Nepal, during 2020 and 2021. Seven different levels of nitrogen (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150 kg/ha), were tested in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The effects of each treatment on yield and yield-attributing traits, NUE, and cost of production were recorded. The application of N above 75 kg/ha did not have significant effects on yield and yield components. Nitrogen, at 75 kg/ha and above, produced the highest tuber yield and benefit cost ratio. Taking into account the agronomic, economic and NUE factors, N dose of 75 kg/ha along with the FYM 20 t / ha was found optimum for the potato cultivation in Machhapuchhre, Kaski and that dose can be recommended for similar soil and agro ecology of Nepal.

Keywords: Nitrogen, nitrogen use efficiency, potato, yield

INTRODUCTION

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum L.*) is one of the most important staple food and predominant tuber crop in Nepal and plays a vital role in ensuring national food security (Lama et al 2016). It occupies the fifth position in terms of area coverage and the second place in production, as well as the first position in productivity (MoALD 2021). The potential of potato tuber production is largely determined by nitrogen and nitrogenous fertilizer, however, increasing the N consumption rate of the potato plant and the effectiveness of absorbed nitrogen for tuber production has long been a challenge. Low productivity is associated with several edaphoclimatic constraints. One of the main reasons for low productivity is the inefficient use of fertilizers. Crop yield and quality are mainly dependent on the availability of nutrients in the soil. Nitrogen is the key element and the most essential element in determining the potential of Potato (Muleta et al 2019). The application of N fertilizer to the soil enables the balance of N supplies and N demands by crop plants for optimal growth and has the potential to increase the productivity of potato (Vos 2010). Higher N fertilization rates in potato have a positive effect on plant growth parameters, and increase tuber number and yield (Ruza et al 2013). Excess use of N fertilizers results in higher costs, lower returns, and an increased risk of environmental pollution (Timilsina and Vista 2022). Nitrogen management is important both in controlling potato growth and development and in minimizing the risks of groundwater contamination by nitrate and emissions of nitrous oxide, a greenhouse gas (Zebarth and Rosen 2007). Sustaining high crop yields with the least nutrient loss to the environment is a major challenge to potato producers (Westerman 2005). In contrast, crop yields do not increase linearly with nitrogen application rate, resulting in a decrease in N use efficiency (NUE) and

greater N losses (Zhang et al 2012, Moreno et al 2003).

The existing recommended doses of fertilizers for potato production are proving to be suboptimal for attaining higher productivity and need to revise them to optimum and more balanced levels with higher nutrient use efficiency. It is essential to find the optimum dose of nitrogen application to ensure efficient use of this element by plants for better yield. Different varieties may have varying responses to N- fertilizer depending on their agronomic traits. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine the optimal dose of N to increase potato production, nitrogen use efficiency (NUE), and economic returns in the farmer's field to be recommended for the conditions of the middle of the hill in Nepal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

A field experiment was conducted at Machhapuchhre Rural Municipality 06 Lahachowk, Kaski (28 ° 31 'Nordic latitude, 83°92' eastern longitude) from October to March 2020 and 2021. The soil was slightly acidic with sandy loam texture, medium to high range of organic carbon and total nitrogen, high content of available P₂O₅ and medium range of available K₂O (Table 1).

Table 1: Soil physicochemical properties at experimental site before the experiment

Soil parameter	Soil test value	Rating	Analysis Method
Soil Texture Class	Sandy loam	-	Hydrometer (Bouyoucos, 1927)
Soil pH	6.45	Slightly acidic	Potentiometric 1:2.5 (Jackson 1973)
Soil organic matter (%)	3.71	Medium	Walkely Black (Walkely and Black 1934)
Total nitrogen (%)	0.20	Medium	Kjeldahl (Bremner 1982)
Available P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ha)	81	High	Modified Olsen's (Olsen et al 1954)
Extractable K ₂ O (kg/ha)	117	Medium	Ammonium acetate (Jackson 1967)

Experimental setup and crop management

The experimental setup consists of seven treatments comprising seven different levels of nitrogen (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150 kg/ha) allocated in a randomized complete block design with three replication (Table 2). The first treatment (T₁) is considered as a control treatment without nitrogen from chemical source. One of the popular potato varieties 'Janakdev' was planted in the second week of November with a crop geometry of 60 cm × 25 cm in each experimental unit of plot size of 7.2 m². The base dose of 20 t/ha FYM during land preparation, 100 kg/ha P₂O₅ and 60 kg/ha K₂O, through single super phosphate (SSP) and potash muriate (MOP), respectively, was applied in line just before seeding in all experimental units. Throughout the growth of the crop, the experiments received consistent plant protection and other cultural management approaches.

Table 2: Treatment Details of the experiment

S.N	Treatment symbol	Treatment details
1	T1	0:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}
2	T2	25:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}
3	T3	50:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}
4	T4	75:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}
5	T5	100:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}
6	T6	125:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}
7	T7	150:100:60 N:P O :K O kg/ha and 20 t/ha FYM _{2 5 2}

Data Recording and Analysis

Yield and yield components such as tuber yield, number and weight of tubers, plant height, plant vigor, and parameters used to measure the efficiency of nutrient use were recorded at respective crop growth. This study used two parameters of NUE, agronomic N use efficiency (ANUE) and N partial factor productivity (NFPF). Based on yield advantage divided by nitrogen application rate, ANUE was estimated (Cassman et al 1996). In other words, it eliminates the contribution of indigenous N in the soil to NUE.

$$ANUE = \frac{Y_N - Y_0}{\text{Nitrogen Rate}}$$

Where, Y_N = Tuber yield in kg/ha for plots fertilized with nitrogen,

Y_0 = tuber yield in kg/ha of plots not fertilized with nitrogen and

Nitrogen rate = amount of N used in kg/ha

Partial factor productivity was estimated by dividing kg tuber production by kg of applied nutrient in each treatment (Ladha et al 2005). Partial budgeting of N and control treatments was performed considering cultural and fertilizer-related costs for the cultivation on a hectare of land. We fixed the input and labor cost, potato tuber and other related price by local market survey (Lahachowk and Pokhara, Kaski). The B:C ratio was calculated using the following formula (Badal et al 2023). All inputs such as seed, fertilizer, pesticides, land rental value, and laborer wage cost involved in cultivation were considered and valued at current market prices to calculate the cost of production.

$$B: C \text{ ratio} = \text{Gross return} / \text{total cost of cultivation}$$

For variance analysis, the Statistical tool for agricultural research (STAR) version 2.0.1 was used, and the significance was determined using Fisher's least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ (Gomez and Gomez 1984).

RESULTS

Plant Height

Different nitrogen levels significantly influenced the height of potato and increasing trend was observed with the increase in nitrogen levels. The tallest plant height was recorded at a nitrogen level of 150kg/ha, followed by 125 kg / ha, and 100 kg/ha which are statistically similar but

significantly taller than the rest of the other N levels during both consecutive year of the experiment. The combined analysis of plant height from both consecutive years of experiment revealed that application of N above 75 kg/ha did not have any significant effect on plant height of potato.

Table 3: Effects of different levels of nitrogen on yield and yield attributing characters of potato at Machhapuchhre 06 Kaski, 2020

Treatments	Plant Height (cm)	Total Tuber/Plot		Yield (t/ha)
		Number	Weight(Kg)	
T1	46.27 d	420 bc	16.53 d	22.96 d
T2	51.20 cd	428 bc	21.26 c	29.53 c
T3	53.73 c	467 bc	25.28 b	35.11 b
T4	56.40 bc	495 b	28.72 a	39.89 a
T5	57.93 abc	581 a	27.91 a	38.76 a
T6	62.67 ab	452 bc	27.85 a	38.69 a
T7	63.67 a	407 c	25.07 b	34.82 b
Mean	55.98	464	24.66	34.25
CV%	6.95	9.24	5.30	5.30
P Value	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.001
LSD_{0.05}	6.92	76	2.32	3.22

Total number and weight of tubers per plot

Increasing the dose of N increased total number of tubers by up to 100 kg/ha N during first year of the experiment, but N level did not have significant effect on the total number of tubers per plot during the second year of the experiment. The total weight of tubers per plot increased significantly to 75 kg/ha N during first year and up to 100 kg/ha N during the second year of experiment. The combined analysis of two-year data revealed N dose above 75 kg/ha N had no significant effect on total weight of tubers per plot.

Table 4: Effects of different levels of nitrogen on yield and yield attributing characters of potato at Machhapuchhre 06 Kaski, 2021

Treatments	Plant Height (cm)	Total Tuber/Plot		Yield (t/ha)
		Number	Weight (Kg)	
T1	39.40 e	405	12.52 d	17.39 d
T2	47.30 d	433	16.96 c	23.55 c
T3	54.50 c	470	18.98 b	26.36 b
T4	55.47 bc	415	20.54 b	28.53 b
T5	56.27 abc	427	23.61 a	32.79 a
T6	58.50 ab	421	24.25 a	33.68 a
T7	59.40 a	410	24.21 a	33.62 a
Mean	52.98	426	20.15	27.99
CV%	3.42	9.34	5.62	5.62
P Value	0.001	0.5	0.001	0.001
LSD_{0.05}	3.22	NS	2.01	2.79

Tuber Yield

The tuber yield of potato varied significantly with different levels of nitrogen. The tuber yield response was positively correlated with increased doses of N from 0 to 150 kg/ha N in both years of experiment (Figure 1). However, after 75 kg/ha N in 2020 (Table 3) and 100 kg/ha N in 2021 (Table 4) the yield increment rate was not significant. The highest mean tuber yield (36.22 t/ha) was achieved with 125 kg / ha N, but that was statistically similar from 75 to 150 kg/ha N application (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Correlation between mean tuber yield and N levels during 2020 and 2021 at Machhapuchhre 06 Kaski

Figure 3: Effects of different N-levels on potato yield during 2020 and 2021 at Machhapuchhre 06, Kaski

Figure 2: Mean potato tuber yield as influenced by different N during 2020 and 2021 at Machhapuchhre 06 Kaski

Agronomic N Use Efficiency (ANUE)

Increasing the dose of N decreased agronomic N use efficiency (ANUE) during both consecutive years of experiment (Figure 3). In 2020, the highest value of ANUE (263.11) was obtained with the application of 25 kg / ha N, which is statistically similar up to 75 kg / ha N, and the value of ANUE is significantly lower above 75 kg/ha N. The maximum ANUE value was obtained in the second year of the experiment with the application of the lowest N rate, but the ANUE values of 50 to 100 kg/ha N application are statistically similar and the lowest ANUE value was recorded with the application of the highest nitrogen rates. The combined analysis of two-year data revealed that agronomic nitrogen use (ANUE) in potato production increased from 93.67 to 254.84 with a decrease in the N application rate from 150 to 25 kg/ha. The ANUE values from the application of 25 to 75 kg/ha N are statistically similar, ANUE above 75 kg/ha decreased significantly and the lowest ANUE recorded from 150 kg/ha N. From the pattern of ANUE with different levels of N, it was evident that application of N above 75 kg/ha was more lost to the environment than its actual utilization by potatoes.

Figure 3: Effects of different levels of N on agronomic nitrogen use efficiency (ANUE) in potato production during 2020 and 2021 at Machhapuchhre 06, Kaski.

Economic Analysis

Table 5: Shows the detail of total cost of production, net benefits, and benefit cost ratios recorded in different treatments. Based on partial budgeting, the highest net benefit (NRs 986925) and the B:C ratio (2.14) was observed with 125 kg/ha N followed by 100 and 75 kg/ha N.

Table 5: Partial economic analysis of different treatments (N levels) estimated for a hectare of land

N Level (Kg/ha)	Mean tuber yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Value of tuber yield (NRs ha ⁻¹)	Cost of production (NRs ha ⁻¹)	Net Benefit (NRs)	B:C Ratio
0	20.17	806800	455000	351800	0.77
25	26.54	1061600	456375	605225	1.33
50	30.73	1229200	457750	771450	1.69
75	34.21	1368400	459125	909275	1.98
100	35.74	143000	460500	969500	2.11
125	36.22	1448800	461875	986925	2.14
150	34.21	1368400	463250	905150	1.95

DISCUSSION

Optimizing the nitrogen dose reduced the amount of N fertilizers, improved yields, and, hence, increased N use efficiency in potato production. The yield and yield attribute parameters recorded superior in N fertilized plots up to a certain level compared to control treatments. The application of N fertilizer significantly influenced the height of potato and increasing trend was observed with the increase in nitrogen levels. This is because the plant grows vigorously when nitrogen is applied in a relatively large amount. Adhikari 2009, Madhikarmy 1979, and Sharma and Upadhaya 1993 have also reported a similar result. The application of N improves various physiological processes, including cell division and elongation of plant that induce maximum vegetative growth and increase plant height (Rea et al 2019). The appropriate nitrogen probably favored the cellular activities and development that led to increased plant vigor (Timilsina et al 2023). The increase in tuber yield could be attributable to nitrogen application to boost dry matter production, improve growth rate, and promote biomass production (Tolessa 2019). Higher N fertilization rates up to a certain level have a positive effect on plant growth parameters and they increase tuber number and yield of tubers. Also, higher N rates are associated with more foliage and consequently promote photosynthetic action, and hence more translocation to tubers (Kumar et al 2007). Increased yields, on the other hand, could be linked to nitrogen's function in improving yield components (Tolessa 2019). The results of Timilsina et al 2023, Shah et al 2013 and Adhikari 2009 also showed that increasing nitrogen rates increased yield and yield components of different crops. The research result from Ruza et al 2013, Fontes et al 2010 and Adhikari 2009 reported the increased potato tuber yield with nitrogen application up to a certain level. The finding of Adhikari 2009 recommends that in sandy loam soils in Chitwan, Nepal, potato cultivar Kufri Sindhuri yields high at higher level of N (150 kg / ha), while Desiree variety yields higher at 100 kg/ha N.

Our study clearly showed that nitrogen application rate had a significant effect on agronomic nitrogen use efficiency (ANUE), with higher NUE found at lower doses of N. Similar results were reported by Liu et al 2016 and according to that result reduced N application rate improves ANUE in potato. The results of other studies also confirm the reduction of the efficiency of agronomic N use with increased N rate (Darwish et al 2006, Kumar et al 2007, Fontes et al 2010, Lombardo 2020)

CONCLUSION

The nitrogen dose of 75 kg/ha through chemical fertilizer along with 20 t/ha farm yard manure (FYM) was found optimum for potato cultivation and N dose above 75 kg/ha from chemical fertilizer did not have significant effects on the yield and yield components of the potato at farmer's field of Machhapuchhre 06 Kaski farmer's field. Considering the agronomic, economic, and NUE factors, 75 kg/ha N along with 20 t/ha FYM can be recommended to similar soil and agro ecology of Nepal for profitable potato production.

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